

Online Teaching Learning (OTL) Systems/Platforms

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Abstract---After the COVID-19 pandemic, the world was forced to move into an online environment. Everything started to take place online virtually. The teaching and the learning were majorly influenced as everything had to move in from an onsite to an online system. There are many challenges that students have to face while using an online learning system. Thus, this research is majorly focused to study the difficulties and challenges a student have to face while using an online teaching learning platform side by side understanding the usability of the different online teaching learning (OTL) platforms.

Keywords--- OTL, Usability, Online/Onsite Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching and Learning are the branches of an education system. Teaching is helping other people to learn. It is an action while learning is a process. A person who teaches are known by an educator, teacher, trainer, tutor, facilitator, lecturer, etc. While a person who learns are known by learner, student, pupil, scholar, etc. Both their meaning can persist as long as if they stand together because a teacher cannot be a teacher unless he/she has a pupil to teach. Learning is much more broader than sitting on class or reading from blogs or listening to someone. Learning is embracing the knowledge through experiences. And teaching someone is sharing those experiences. So, a teacher is always a learner at the very beginning. But, talking about the teaching/learning systems. There are basically two kinds of teaching or learning methods. They are:

- Onsite Teaching/Learning
- Online Teaching/Learning

Onsite Teaching and Learning is the training provided to a person in a teaching and learning environment that is arranged by the organization. The environment can be class, halls or an enclosed room where teacher and students are present. The main feature of an onsite teaching learning environment is that the course instructor can interact with the student both verbally and non-verbally. The interaction of student teacher and their expressiveness is more when it comes to onsite learning teaching environment. Onsite Learning helps to enhance the critical thinking skills among the students. One can collaborate with the other through eye contacts and generate new and noble ideas through healthy discussions. It helps build social skills among the students as one student is directly indulged with other through physical and verbal communications. This builds up relationship and develops social skills with one another. Besides few of these advantages onsite learning has several other features and advantages while also has many disadvantages too.

Online teaching learning (OTL) refers to teaching particular courses completely online over the internet without the physical presence of both teacher and students. It is also referred as e-learning. There are several platforms to carry out online teaching learning process. There are no physical or on-campus class sessions in an online teaching environment. Educational, business and may other institutions use online teaching learning environment when they have participants coming from multiple locations that are not geographically close to each other. The online teaching and learning environment is often practiced when we want to take the

teaching and learning beyond the classroom. Basically, the main advantage of an online teaching learning environment can be that a student who is enrolled in the course can take the course at any time in the day for anywhere in the world. The enrolled person will also have unlimited access to the courses as well. They can have the freedom to take more than one course at a time too. The collaboration with one other students is not limited to class room sessions only. Similarly, there are several other advantages and disadvantages of online teaching learning system as well.

A. Components of OTL

An OTL system is a complete package comprised basically of five components for an effective online teaching learning system. Let us visualize how the components are related with each other on an OTL system. The visualization is represented by Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Components of an OTL System

The components are:

1) Audience

Audience are the primary component of an Online Learning Teaching System. Audience use the OTL system directly or indirectly. The most prominent audiences of an Online Teaching Learning System are:

a) Course Instructors

Course Instructors are the particular group of people on an online teaching learning platform who are basically responsible in instructing or teaching the learners of the platforms. They post videos, assignments, links, slides and many other resources to help the students learn on a friendly manner. They also give out online teaching sessions along with personal interviews too.

b) Learners

The Learners are those group of people who use the platform basically to learn particular course from particular instructor. The learners seek for information, ask questions to

the instructors, appear online exams and even communicate with their fellow course learners.

c) Administrator

Administrator may be bunch of people or a single person who is responsible for managing and handling different operations on the platform. They are responsible to solving

2) Course Structure

The structure of the course defines how the courses are made. The course consists of many things like assignments, slides, projects, etc. One should follow the order of the other. Because, generally courses are taught at the beginning and assignments and slides are given to help understand the topics better. And, projects are given at the end to sum all the learned contents from the particular course. Various course structures are:

a) Logical Course Hierarchy

The courses must follow logical hierarchy. Because, a user who wants to enroll into particular course should know where the courses must be. Hierarchical course structures make the courses easily fetchable.

b) Table of Contents

The table of contents make the course very easy to fetch. They are similar to the hierarchical structure explained above. But, they are however defined at the very beginning of the courses hierarchy are followed throughout the course.

c) Module Size

The main idea of making modular is dividing contents into small sizes so that students or the learners don't feel it's too much and unmotivated. Rather, making it modular will help them see their progress after they have completed particular content. And, it makes them feel achieve even more. So, they tend to take other courses when courses are made modular.

d) Graphics and Animations

On the user view level, the animations and graphics are the most important part. It is what attracts the users to use particular platform. Because, currently you can find a lot of platforms for online learning. But, it is what the graphics and animations that help attract the users. So, they are the very important components.

3) Page Design

OTL systems are accessed on any devices. Either on laptops, mobile phones, tablets and many other. Since they are the web applications, the page designing are the most important part. The height, width are dynamic according to the device we prefer to use them on. So, it is an important component. Some examples where page design should be applied are:

a) Graphics, Fonts, Layouts, Sizes

Each of the mentioned components are necessary to be defined because a user is not constrained over particular devices to use the platform on to visualize the courses. The fonts and layouts should be dynamic according to the use screen too.

b) Balance Design

The design should be balanced. Because, too much design also freaks out the user. Just like keeping it simple, simple designs would be enough to attract the users to use the platform. It's just that there should be the balance between the designs and the contents and one should not overlap the other.

platform issues. They take feedback from students and course instructors and even try to build platform to its optimum operating level. They may or may not necessarily be the developer of the platform.

c) Navigation and Control

Navigations are generally the most important part. Because, they are the ones which tell user where the particular courses are. Using the top navigation bar or the side navigation bar helps a lot. But sometimes, there is the use of too much navigations which makes things difficult because searching through navigation becomes complicated.

4) Content Engagement

It refers to the measure of interactivity a particular learner of the course has with the platform. Generally, OTL systems become dull because they lack particular things that affect the level of interactivity. Students generally have a habit of taking or starting too many courses at once but they are mostly able to finish only few of the courses. Because, they find that the interactivity of the courses to decrease when they are midway through on the course. So, various components are there to increase the content engagement.

a) Achievements and Badges

A particular example of Achievements and Badges can be Stack overflow, Coursera, etc. They have incorporated badges as a measure to the achievements. We all want to achieve more and more. So, things like badges really help us to measure our progress and we feel more into the courses. We want to achieve more and more and we really use it more often.

b) Graphics and Animations

Graphics and Animations are effective in every field. When graphics and animations are dynamic, the increase courses interactions among the users too. They are one of the primary reason for doing the courses.

c) Quizzes and Interview

Coursera has a quiz once the topics are over on every courses. This is one of the fundamental example to involve one's interactivity with particular course because we want to test our knowledge by doing the quiz. If they have also kept some interviews of person who have achieved a lot on their particular field, it also helps to increase one's interactivity to the courses.

5) Usability

Usability is the condition between the system and the user when the users feel safe, effective and efficient to use the particular system. It is necessary for a platform to have the above property. A platform should never violate the user's privacy. Following properties can be present.

a) Recommendation System

A good platform always recommends courses to the user of user's interests. The interest of the users are found generally by the implementations of various machine learning algorithms. So, that at the end they are capable of performing collaborative or content based filtering to recommend good courses to the users of users choices.

b) Notifications

A platform has an option for subscription too. When we subscribe, we subscribe the newsletters, new courses blogs and many more. These help the learners or the subscribers be updated with the platform too.

c) Forums

Forums can act as a medium to build connection with other fellow learners of the platform. This can increase communication skills of the user too. Creating relations with the people of same field will be helpful in future too.

d) Project Development

Besides coursework, the platforms can also be used to do some Project Developments. Implementation of project development features leads the platform to be used not only while doing the course only but also using the platform when doing several projects in the future, generally like gigs these days.

B. Importance of OTL systems

There are several importance of OTL systems. Some of their importance are:

1) Convenience:

There is a flexibility in access of course 24/7 from any online computers anywhere.

2) Enhanced Learning

According to research, there is a increased depth of understanding and retention of course content on online learning platforms. The technology skills, writing skills are more likely to improve too.

3) Leveling of the play field

On an online learning environment, students can take more time to think and answer particular questions with time too. Also, introvert student are more likely to express themselves through the medium of online learning system.

4) Innovative Teaching

The teaching and learning can be done on an innovative environment. The activities like quizzes, coding sessions can be more effective than the onsite sessions.

5) Interaction

A personalized collaborative environment can improve both the student-teacher interaction and student-student interaction. The mediums like forums, private messages and calls can help the interaction to be even better.

6) Outreach

More students are like to enroll into the course because the compulsion of attending classes is not present. So, any student can enroll any courses any time. Hence, the outreach is also enhanced.

7) Environmental Impact

The online learning teaching system can be done without public gathering. The pollution impact is reduced too. It can be paper less as everything is online. So, Environmental purpose also shows, OTL systems as better for environment.

8) Repeatability

The courses online can be accessed as much number of times we like repeatedly. Unlike, campus based class systems, where if we miss something we have no better option then asking the mentor. Here, repeatability is one of the primary importance of the OTL systems.

C. Types of OTL System

1) Blended Learning

It is a blend between the in-person classroom time and the individual study online using e-learning software. It involves tutor-led activities, images, videos, quizzes, assignments, digital tasks and face to face discussion on class room environment. There is a presence of dedicated instructor on class room environment who also offer other learning opportunities on the digital platform. Basically, it's the combination of both the traditional and modern style of teaching. Students come with different requirements and since it has both, it seems to be more effective among the students too.

2) Active Learning

It is a teaching strategy where all the students are involved as an active participants during the learning process. Students sit passively and listen to the expert of particular domain. Various teaching approaches it involves are: journal writing, problem solving and paired discussions, case-studies, role plays, etc. It is brought in practice because through this type of learning system, interactive and integrative, collaborative active learning experiences and personal development among the students can be achieved. Thus this type of teaching systems become effective.

3) Engaged Learning

In this type of learning, the students actively participate in their learning. Learning environment like that practiced in many parts of the world, from the first day, the students are clearly involved in the decision making of their course of study. Students involve in research, discussions and technological projects to bring changes in the world. The students are actively involved in the learning process and the teacher serve as a instructor, coach or facilitator.

4) Personalized Learning

It is a learning environment where the main idea is to provide each student with different learning experience on the basis of their skills, activities, choices, background and domain. Personalized learning occurs on an fine Learning Management System like: MOOC, Canvas, K-12. A recommendation engine is used on a personalized learning system to enhance the student experience. Content based and Collaborative filtering is used for the recommendation of the contents on a personalized learning system.

5) Flipped Course Learning

It is a learning teaching system which consists maximum involvement of the students rather than the course instructors. These type of teaching learning system focus on self-learning to get knowledge. Here, the teaching materials like: videos, slides, pdfs, files, links and other resources are provided to the students at the earliest. And, student appear the class with the knowledge of the particular content given to study. And, in the classes the teachers and students discuss on the problems faced by the students while going through the resources provided. In this way, both the teacher and students learn on an effective manner. Mini lecture series are also given to the students when they are confused on subject matters. This type of learning systems has also been proved to be effective.

6) Web-Based Learning/ Online Classes

They are generally performed on the web only. They are also referred as online classes. Here, the course instructors shares the contents only on the web. The course instructor hosts a meeting and everyone are invited into the meeting. The

instructor teach the students and give out assignments and discuss them on consecutive next sessions. This is how the Web-Based Learning take place.

II. DESIGN ISSUES OF THE OTL SYSTEMS

According to WizIQ, the ten characteristics of highly effective online teaching system are[1]:

a) Simple and Streamlined

The system is simple and straight forward whose sole purpose is to fulfill the user needs and requirements.

b) User-Friendly

The OTL systems are user-friendly focusing on highest usability of a user. They are efficient and effective. The learning curve is painless too. The graphics and animations really make things different.

c) Attractive Interface

The users are attracted by the attractive interface. So, a OTL systems has an attractive interface by the implementations of graphics and animations. Picture speaks thousand words. Use of pictures and pictorial representations make the interface attractive.

d) Compelling Course Pages

The home pages of the courses are like magnets. The pull learners into them. They are made and built attractive so that any user dive into the course immediately after going through the home pages.

e) Embedded

The course pages has many embedded features too. The use of this embedded features make the courses interactive. They turn a particular page into an animated pages.

f) Easy to flip

Courses are built on a fashion that actually may not follow an order. This means that a course that is being taught on slides can also be taught by video lectures too. These sudden implementations make it easy to flip.

g) Time-Zone Friendly

The courses are time-zone friendly and consistent because we can access the particular courses anytime from anywhere in the world. The contents is consistent and completely opposite to on campus traditional teaching methodologies.

h) Socially Driven

Those students who have hard time interacting with other students feel more easy to express themselves in front of the camera. By the use of messaging systems and forums, they are socially driven for every students using the Online Teaching Learning system.

i) A fully-integrated online School

The Online Teaching Learning system has even developed the capacity to graduate people these days. So, they are no different than the Traditional onsite learning schools. As they consist the same instructors, their same lectures and slides, the same assignments, everything same but in a different pattern. So, they are the fully-integrated Schools.

j) Social Sharing Capabilities

The contents and achievements can be shared on various social medias like: Facebook, twitter, LinkedIn etc. This

allows the courses to have a reach among a large sum of population. The course has a feedback option too. So, while reaching out to large group of people, large feedbacks are achieved too which in turn help the platform develop.

These were the various characteristics of an Effective Online Teaching Learning System as shared on the blog.

D. Design Issues

So, after we discussed on the characteristics of an Online Teaching Learning System, we came to know what comprises the online teaching learning system. So, it is necessary to design a system with the above characteristics. But, while developing a system with the above characteristics, several design issues may occur. The various design issues that occurs while designing the system are [2]:

1) Heterogeneity

The online teaching learning system is hosted on the internet. The internet allows different sort of users to access the platform through different services and different environments. The platforms can be accessed over mobile phones, computers and different other mediums. The different mediums have a different physical and data link layers. For an example, the phone uses WIFI, while computers use ethernet or WIFI. That is there is heterogenous collections of computers and networks. But, their differences are masked by a single fact which is that all of them use internet protocols(IPs) to communicate with one another. Different local internet protocols are subsequent branches of a global internet protocols. But, besides the fact of difference in protocols, they all communicate with each other. Also, besides these contents, the heterogeneity also defines the following things:

a) What device is used to access the platform?

b) Which operating system you use to access the platform?

c) What database is present on the platform?

d) Who are the targeted users, etc.?

2) Openness

The openness has a similar concept of the open source. Openness is the characteristics that allows the user to access the platform from administrative perspective and reimplement it in various ways so as to make it better and better. The contributors are not necessarily the original developers of the platform. The contributors can be anyone who frequently use the platform or anyone who seek to contribute public projects for the betterment of others. The level of openness is still determined by the amount of resources shared to the user or client view level. The openness is based on the following:

a) How much resources are shared to the users and client view level?

b) Can others contribute for the platform's progress?

c) How security issues can be handled?

3) Security

Privacy is our greatest wealth. At the time we sign up for the platform, we are asked to submit the various details. Things like our name, birthday, photo, emails, etc. are our

private contents. We can't afford it to be publicly available on the internet. Security is our major concern. Besides that too, we are asked to fill various agreement forms too. These things can really bring out various vulnerabilities. The security for important resources has mainly three important components. The diagram representation of the three important components to ensure security is represented by Fig. 2.

- a) Confidentiality
- b) Integrity
- c) Availability

Fig. 2. Security

The various constraints that define the security of the platform are:

- d) Does it save password?
- e) Does it have information encryption system?
- f) Does the website bear SSL certifications?
- g) How many server ports are opened?

4) Scalability

Scalable is a property which defines that whether a platform will remain the same and effective if the number of resource and user increases. When the amount of resources increase, problem of memory occurs. But, the system should be capable of running same as before only then it has scalable memory. And also, with the increase in the number of users of the system, the user request to the server may also increase. The following constraints is able to define whether the systems are scalable or not.

- a) Does increase in number of resources cause database management issues?
- b) Does increase in the amount of user requests cause delay in response time or latency in response?

5) Failure Handling

Sometimes due to uneven conditions and unexpected issues, the server may fall down too. The website and applications may be down. On a well-built system with hundreds of clients, this type of problems can really cause mess. We may even loose clients if we are not able to handle the failures. A very good example of failures are the DDOS attacks on the server. These types of attack cause multiple requests on the server and because of this, the server is not able to respond and remain down. Restarting the server could take time. So, a backup plan should be made. When failures occur, maintenance page should be developed so as to aware the users. Multiple servers or use of distributed systems should be there to avoid failure. The constraints that measure failure handling are:

- a) Is the maintenance page present?

- b) Are Secondary servers or distributed systems present?

6) Concurrency

Fig. 3. Concurrency

A server host the resources. Multiple devices are able to access the same resources, which is referred to as the concurrency. The resources are shared while not defined differently to different devices. Following constraints are able to define whether concurrency is met or not? Fig. 3. displays the concurrency on different devices for accessing the same resource.

- a) How many computer systems can be connected to the server?
- b) How is the response time of the server for such huge number of computer systems?

7) Transparency

Fig. 4. Transparency

There are different view levels. The view level that appears to the clients and the user is different compared to the view level that appears to the administrator or the course instructor. It is the administrator who sets the transparency level to the user or the client of the system. It should be necessarily defined what contents should be defined to the users. The most easiest technique is to hide the distribution from the users. There are several forms of transparency that are present on a distributed systems. They are:

i) *Location Transparency*: The users are not able to tell where the resources are located in this form of transparency.

ii) *Migration Transparency*: The resources can be moved by the users according to the will without changing the names of the resources.

iii) *Replication Transparency*: The users are not able to tell how many copies are present in this form of transparencies.

iv) *Concurrency Transparency*: In this transparency, multiple users are able to share the resources automatically.

v) *Parallelism Transparency*: This form of transparency states that several activities happen in parallel without the consent of the users.

Above types of Transparency is represented on Fig. 4.

Following constraints are defined to measure the transparency:

a) *How much details of other users should be made available to one another?*

b) *What notifications should the users need to be notified?*

c) *How much personal details should the user be given to view?*

8) *Quality of Service*

Quality of service is determined by the reliability, security and performance of a system. Once the systems are developed and starts to function well, their qualities are also defined. The quality is not always the same standard. With time, there can be compromise in the quality of service. For example with time and new other products on the market, the particular system may have to adapt some other extra features so that they can stay better among others. The constraints that define the quality of service are:

a) *Are reliability, security and performance at the same level of development?*

b) *Does the system bring out agility?*

9) *Reliability*

The main goals of building a full functional online teaching learning system is to make them reliable than the online teaching learning system currently already into existence. The main idea is that our online teaching learning system is more efficient and effective than the online teaching learning system already in market. The data entrusted to the system by the users must not be lost in any cases. However, the OTL systems are prone to failure because any vulnerable activities for users or attackers and any malicious contents may lead the server down. So, if one server goes down, other should be able to handle the situation. In case, any files get missing that should be retrieved immediately because that may contain sensitive user information. Following constraints are able to define the reliability of the system:

a) *How many backup servers are present?*

b) *What servers the computers are running?*

c) *What are the available ports open?*

d) *Are the platforms vulnerable to cross-site scripting (XSS)?*

10) *Performance*

Performance is the main challenge of the system. Because, solving design issues related to transparency, flexibility, reliability and other properties may really bring out a problem in performance. Because, backing up the contents and bringing out memory usage may however increase the response time of the system to the user input. Basically, performance of the system cannot be compromised while adding different features. Also, sometime too much JavaScript and animations on the websites may make it slower to respond on the internet. So, in this cases the performances are compromised. The various constraints that define the performance are:

a) *How fast is the platform?*

b) *What language is used in back end?*

c) *How is database management done?*

d) *How much animations and graphics are incorporated on the platform?*

III. CHALLENGES OF ONLINE TEACHING LEARNING SYSTEM

There are several advantages of online teaching learning system. Flexibility, convenience and consistency being the major ones. But, the online teaching learning system is lot more challenging than it actually seem. Online teaching learning system may seem like more effortless to both the students and teachers. But, in reality, online teaching learning system require just as much energy and time as traditional classroom learning system. It also requires extra computer skills and learning strategies in order to succeed. The various challenges of Online Teaching Learning System are[1]:

A. *Persistence*

Persistence can be the biggest key to success for an online teaching learning system. Only those students are able to succeed on online learning teaching system, who are able to dedicate their time and efforts to the platform on a regular basis. The students willing to tolerate technical problems, perform assignments and tasks and follow the courses daily can succeed. The students most have following:

a) *When the students get stuck on a problem or challenges, students need to keep trying and ask for help with the mentors.*

b) *Students need to set up a manageable schedule for themselves and always stick with it. Students who log in and make progress everyday are only able to succeed.*

B. *Accessibility*

It can be the main challenge for an online teaching learning system. Because, for us to be connected with the courses and platform, we need internet. And, all the parts of the country are not provided with a good connection to the internet which can act as a problem to directly connect with the course and the course mentor. Generally, the problem of the internet arise to the people living in rural areas. So, talking only about rural areas, a person may be connected to the internet by using several data packs or through ADSL networks. But still, the speed of the internet using this medias is quite slow. And, large bandwidth is consumed on live video sessions by the course instructors. So, the solution can be following:

a) *Providing the offline learning contents*

b) Decreasing size of video files by decreasing quality

C. Effective Time-Management Skills

The class notice are already informed a day before. But, the main problem is we tend to miss the class because the online class sessions are mostly irregular and organized only on the free times of the Course Instructors. Due to this, we generally tend to forget the date and time. Students may not be able to manage time effectively because during onsite sessions, the students were used to receiving constant pressures from the teachers, but this does not happen while they are at home. So, the students generally tend to procrastinate their schedules. So, effective management skills doesn't happen which needs to happen. We can do the following things to develop a habit.

a) Always reviewing the syllabus at the time of starting of the assignments and developing a plan on how long time the assignments will take on applying constant effort every day.

b) Making a daily TO-DO check list a day earlier or in the morning and following the TO-DO list.

D. Effective and Appropriate Communication Skills

The Communication skills are the most vital part in online teaching learning because students must seek help when they are stuck on situations. The Teachers are always willing to help the students, but they are also unable in situations where they have to pick up on non-verbal clues, such as a look of confusion on a student's face because sometimes the students might be feeling nervous, shaky, afraid, etc. It is easier to find out in onsite sessions while in online sessions, these things are hard to catch. But, following things can be done too:

a) Using the tools provided to communicate with the course instructor

Many platforms provide several ways for students and/or parents to communicate with teachers and staff. Various modes of communication between teachers and students might include e-mail, discussion groups, chat room office hours, cell phones, and even text messaging. We can ask the teachers even when it is not teaching hours. We can just leave a message and the teacher will answer them on their free time.

b) Using appropriate language for communication

When communicating with the course instructors and other staffs, one should write in full, grammatically correct sentences and with a respectful tone. Many students prefer writing the messages and emails on an informal language knowingly or unknowingly. This should be avoided. The course instructors should be treated with respect and courtesy.

E. Basic Technical Skills

During Onsite classes, technical skills were not given a major concern. The onsite classes were traditional and the teaching and learning was only done on paper, board using markers and pens. The technical methods like online sessions, surveys, forums are not quite often used and if even used, they are used by very limited course instructors. Due to this the technical problem might arise while communicating. Thus at the beginning of the sessions like these, it is must to give instructions or personal guidance so that the students and teachers both can be familiar with the online teaching learning

platform. Such guidance can be referred from the colleges websites or other platforms too.

F. Reading and Writing Skills

By reading and writing, it means on the computer screen. One may not have a habit of reading from the screen. Generally, the students or the learners tend to seek knowledge through books and notes. They may not have a habit of reading from the computer screen or through Pdfs. The blue light emitted by the screen can really be a problem for the beginners. It is really a challenging task.

While writing on the computer screen, one should have at least a typing rate of 25-30 words per minute to cope up with the platform assignments and take notes given by the teacher. If writing speed is compromised, it can really be troublesome while taking notes and while doing the assignments given by the course instructors.

G. Motivation and Independence

Motivations make you hunger for dreams and recognitions. Here, the main motivation is the want to succeed the course by finishing the course. Online teaching learning, basically the learning requires independence, internal motivation, responsibility and certain levels of maturity too. Because, is it why we joined computer engineering or any particular subject that we are currently studying because we really wanted to? Or Family pressures were present? Money can be a motivation. The most challenging task is to build up the motivation and self-awareness that determines we really wanted to do what we are currently doing. The main motivations for working hard are:

a) to achieve good grades in final examinations

b) to have a greater level of satisfaction with our future career

c) for personal pride

d) to seek wide level of opportunities including higher studies and higher income

H. A Good Study Environment

For being able to think properly, a good study environment must be present. Only on a silence and motivating environment, one is able to think and work properly. The various components that constitute a good study environment are:

a) Peace and Quiet

We need a peaceful environment to work on without the disturbance from television, friends and family on a quiet environment.

b) Avoid Games

We should not really play games or get distracted by others playing games while we are studying and doing our projects.

c) Turn off your cell phone

The notifications on the cell phones are really disturbing. When some notification pings in, we leave our work and get into the notifications. Sometimes, someone might even call us

on the phone and disturb us for a long time. Due to these facts, the cell phones should be turned off.

d) Beware Surfing

It is the black hole of the internet. Because, we get lost into the internet once we start surfing the contents. The internet just gets deeper and deeper. We would not know how much time we lapsed using the internet. This is known as beware surfing.

e) Consider Ergonomics

We should adjust the height of our chair, keyboard, and screen so that you are comfortable using the computers. The Forearms and thighs should also be leveled and parallel to the floor. Our wrists should not be bent while we are typing.

f) Setting up good lighting and comfortable seating

The good lighting makes a person more cheerful. More cheerful the person is, more ideas generate on mind. Seating should also be made comfortable because efficiency increases on comfortable seating and works. The lighting should be no more brighter than the environmental light. Because they can provide stress on the eye.

IV. ONLINE TEACHING LEARNING SYSTEMS

As Learning is skills or knowledge which acquired through study, experience or being taught. The Online learning is the reimagining of the educational process that is able to maximize available virtual classroom software to engage geographically-ranged students fully. The online teaching learning system brings flexibility into the process regarding scheduling, content availability, and structures, which allows students to access the learning material when and where they choose at any time. There are several categories of online teaching learning systems.

The logically group and sub-group of existing OTL systems based on nature of services, modes of services, open source and professional online teaching learning systems can be represented by a hierarchical diagram on Fig. 5.

Basis for Proposing the above Hierarchical structure:

A. *Nature of Services*

The nature of service of a platform can be as an administrator, a mentor or the tutor.

a) Administrator

The primary work of the administrator to provide service is sending down notifications, handling the sites and contents misuse.

b) Mentor

There are special persons to help on the platforms who provide feedbacks and also help in time of necessities. Queries can be asked to them.

c) Tutor

Tutor is the person responsible for teaching the courses. They are the primary person involved in teaching.

Consider the example of Coursera, Mr. Andrew-Ng is the tutor, Yan Le Chun is the mentor for some particular courses. While developers might be the admins on the back end.

B. *Mode of Services*

The various mode of services are:

a) Virtual Classrooms

They provide class room like environment in the presence of tutor and the student. Several topics are discussed, questions are asked and answered. Example: on platforms like zoom, google class room, etc.

b) Web Based Learning

The learning activity occurs on websites or web apps in the presence of internet. We login in to the personalized learning sites and then learn various courses and materials. Popular examples of web based learning are: Coursera, Khan Academy, etc.

c) Offline Learning

Generally, the learnings nowadays are web based but there are some platforms too that provide offline based learning. One very old and popular example of the offline based learning is the Encarta.

d) Mobile Learning

Mobile learning is learning portably through anyplace at any time. It does not necessarily mean learning through mobile phones. They are learning through devices that can be attached and detached from any places. The popular examples are: Coursera, Zoom, Moodle, Teams, etc.

e) Collaborative Learning

Collaborative Learning is learning through communicating with persons of similar aims and interests. Talking and generating new ideas really help collaborative learning sessions to be successful. The examples are the audio and video calling applications like: Zoom, Team, Skype, etc.

C. *Open-Source Services*

The open source defines the degree of freedom that the applications provide for their reuse and development. They are of various types:

a) Complete Open Source

The applications whose source codes are easily available on the internet are referred to as the fully opensource applications. They can be reused and reimplemented to make it even better. Their primary aim is not selling and earning. Their license are completely free. They are profit less applications. The one popular example of opensource learning platform is the Wikipedia.

b) Partial Open Source

Some applications are made partially opensource. They are made partially opensource because the developers think that there is still chance of improvements which the developers or the owner want it to happen. They want new applications with new features to be

Fig. 5. Hierarchical Diagram representing the Categories of OTL Systems

developed without losing the previous values. Moodle systems can be the popular example of partially opensource online teaching learning platform.

c) Full Paid

Most of the online teaching learning platforms are full paid only. They are profit motive organization. They seek to earn profit on the way providing good services too. Several financial aids are also present on their platforms. But, the courses are generally more expensive and affording them can be a problem for the poor. Their primary objective is to earn more subscribers. The popular examples of full paid online teaching learning platforms are: Udemy, edX, etc.

D. Professional Systems

The online teaching learning platforms offered to the user after signup is a complete new system. It is incorporated with help and guidance on how to use the system. Sometimes online chat bots are present too. The two professional systems are:

a) Standard System

The standard system as the name suggests has a standard to everything. Including the sizes of the fonts, the dimensions of the images, page numbers, layouts, etc. All are made standard. Such system are not customizable by the user of the system. The user can only use the system as they follow particular standard only. E.g. Zoom, Coursera, etc.

b) Customizable System

The systems that can be customizable by the users after signups are called the customizable systems. Generally, the customizations are done on the front end while the customization on the backend can be done only to user information only. The customization on the backend can be

done by the developers of the system only. Besides, the customization can only be done on fonts, layouts, image sizes, etc. Moodle can be an example of customizable system. The Moodle system even allows adding extra plugins to the platform itself too.

A. Various OTL Systems

There are various OTL systems. Some of them are:

1) Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment)

A learning management system (LMS) is a software application for the administration, documentation, tracking, reporting, and delivery of educational courses, training programs, or learning and development programs[1]. As per the need of individual students, the learning must be personalized. The term personalized learning, or personalization, refers to a diverse variety of educational programs, learning experiences, instructional approaches, and academic support strategies that are intended to address the distinct learning needs, interests, aspirations, or cultural backgrounds of individual students[2]. Moodle is one of the basic example of the Learning Management System that is open source in nature.

There are several users present on a Moodle system who send requests to the Moodle Web Server. The Moodle Web Server uses PHP server. Upon the requests of the users the Moodle Web Server sends requests to the Moodle Database Server. The Moodle Database Server uses RDBMS, MYSQL, Oracle, Microsoft SQL Server and PostgreSQL as well. Moodle architecture can be visualized in Fig. 6.

The various features of the Moodle system are:

a) File Sharing

We can upload the files and share it among the other participants on a Moodle System. The files can be uploaded directly as well as, various drive links like google drive links, one drive links can also be kept on the Moodle system too. Collaborative file sharing is not present on the older versions.

b) Private Domain Facility

Moodle system allocates separate domain facility to different classrooms so that separate classrooms have separate domains or the separate websites. Hence, they are also used to create private websites too.

c) Miscellaneous Features

Besides the facility of separate domain and file sharing facility, the Moodle also provides other various miscellaneous features. The various Moodle features are:

PERSONALIZED DASHBOARDS

The Moodle systems are customizable systems. Their dashboards can be customized according the user choices.

NOTIFICATION HANDLER

Moodle system can be incorporated with the separate email plugin that is able to send notifications of the classroom on to the email. This can be treated as an extra plugin.

PRIVATE MESSAGING

Moodle Systems are also capable of sending private messages to other fellow users of the Moodle systems. But, in the older versions the resources could not be shared.

SIMPLE TEXT EDITOR

Moodle system has also incorporated an extra plugin that consists of a simple text editor. The simple text editor is capable of taking notes and can be treated as sticky notes to add reminders.

PROGRESS TRACKING

The Moodle system has a feature that can track our progress. The no. of mouse clicks we made, the no. of times we opened a certain link, our login and logout details. Even the newer version of the Moodle system can also predict the marks that we will obtain on the basis of our track records on the platform.

CALENDAR

The calendar is another plugin present on the Moodle system which acts as a timer and reminder on our deadlines and assignments by sending us notifications. It is one of its primary feature too.

B. Google Classroom

Google classroom is probably one of the most advanced online teaching learning platform currently present. Google has given it all to make it better and better. Google has a very

wide branch relating to data management which may also be the reason why file sharing is one of the prominent features of Google. The files can be shared and edited at the same time on Google platform. The file sharing system is promoting collaborative works among each other and tutors and students. The Google classroom uses google drives, google docs, google sheets, etc. on a very modular and a simple platform. This is really help us to go paperless. Moreover, the google class room also has a plagiarism feature checker. Because of this feature, the readable inputs can be checked with plagiarism tools. Also, when each classes are held, a separate drive folder for that class rooms are made. Because of this modularity feature, files can be accessed by both the students and teachers easily. Also, the google calendars being one of the most prominent feature used not only by google class room but most of the people in the world to manage schedules and arrange meetings and interviews. The Google Classroom architecture can be visualized here in Fig. 7.

The features can be discussed in points as:

1) Plagiarism Checker

There is a tool called Originality Reports which is present on the google classroom platform. The google developers have made a use of the plagiarism checker in their platform so as to ensure whether the students have copied or plagiarized each other's contents or not.

2) File Sharing

Like already discussed earlier, the google drive is one of the most preferred file sharing options throughout the world. The files can be shared on real time and also be edited by one another on real time. This is its very prominent feature.

3) Google Calendar

The google calendars are also one of the most prominent features used not only by google class room but most of the people in the world to manage schedules and arrange meetings and interviews.

4) Tracking Progress

The google classroom has a feature that can track our progress. The no. of mouse clicks we made, the no. of times we opened a certain link, our login and logout details. Google can even search our history to see the sites we have been into to track our progress.

5) Other Extra Features

The Google classroom being a google product can offer various extra features too. The features are online GPU for working with data, online video conferencing through google meets, online video players, file openers, etc. There

Fig. 6. Moodle System

Fig. 7. Google Classroom

Fig. 8. MOOC (Massive Open Online Course)

are several many other feature that are provided by the google.

C. MOOC (Massive Open Online Course):

In other terms MOOCs can be referred to as personalized learning platforms. As per the student's need, the learning must be personalized. Personalized learning refers to the diverse variety of educational programs, learning experiences, instructional approaches and academic support strategies which are intended to address the distinct learning needs, interests, aspirations or cultural backgrounds of the individual students. Similarly, MOOC is one of the most important

personalized learning platforms that has helped many students, learners and enthusiasts throughout the world to gain knowledge and prosper in their fields. The main features of Personalized learning include managing learning content, managing user roles, delivering user contents, finding learning goals, accessing learning contents can checking the learning progress. The Moodle architecture can be visualized in Fig. 8.

Various MOOCs that are actively present throughout the world are:

1) Coursera

The Co-founder of Coursera is a popular scientist and researcher Andrew-Ng. Coursera's pioneer courses are based on machine learning but currently several topics are being covered and it has stand up to earning \$145 million revenue a year.

2) Udacity

Udacity is similar to coursera. The courses on Udacity are mostly premium and too expensive to afford for normal people.

3) Udemy

Udemy is another platform similar to Udacity which is hugely profit motive too. The basic courses are free while the premium courses are too expensive even ranging up to \$400.

4) edX

The edX is an established online learning platform. It is established by the scientists and AI researchers from Columbia University. The courses present on edX are of great values and difficult for normal person to complete.

5) Khan Academy

It is one of the oldest platform whose contents container is so huge. Often discarded by its name but the contents on Khan Academy are productive and helpful.

Several Features of the MOOC are:

a) Certifications

The reason why MOOCs are so successful may be because most people search for certifications rather than learning. They want certifications on the way while they are learning. MOOCs tend to provide recognizable certifications to the students who are able to complete particular courses.

b) Financial Aids

The MOOCs like coursera are able to provide financial aids too. Because of this whole community if enthusiasts are able to learn contents from the platform. This may be the reason, why MOOCs are putting value to student's lives.

c) Recognized Course Instructors

Most of the time, the MOOCs are able to organize courses and teachings from the founders of the particular courses too. For an example, Andrew Ng is one of the most recognized person when it comes to AI and his courses are completely free too. There are several similar examples which is the reason why we tend to use MOOC.

d) Video and Audio Lectures

The MOOCs provide various series of Audio and Video lectures. The video lectures are self-explainable and very easier to understand. Because of this, we tend to choose video audio lectures over self-readings.

D. ZOOM

Zoom is video and audio conferencing application generally used for online teachings, conferences and interviews. Zoom is also recognized as the most widely used video conferencing application at the time of Covid-19 pandemic. Zoom is the major source of communication during this period. It is a desktop and mobile application. One or more person host the meeting and several others join the meeting. There is the presence of zoom usernames and password on the basis of which the participant log into the meeting. If direct join link is sent to the participants then the passwords are not required. Zoom is very light and consumes very less bandwidth. Previously during its launch, the zoom let only 40 minutes of audio video sessions for free users. Currently, newer updates support very long video sessions too. Zoom is also regarded as the future of work from home technology. The ZOOM architecture can be visualized in Fig. 9.

The various features of Zoom are:

1) Host/Admin Control

The Host or the Admin is able to kick out participants if they act unevenly. Moreover, they are also allowed to turn the mikes and videos in case of situations. In the newer updates, the host need to admit the participants before they can enter classroom.

2) Security

Security was measure concern at the time of launch of Zoom application because anyone with the link could barge into the meeting. Now, due to additional features, the host has an option of whether to admit the participants on to the meeting or not. However, user data is always a concern as Zoom is a Chinese based application.

3) Cross Platform

Zoom is cross platform application because it can run on personal computers as well as mobile phones without any memory issues. Memory handling is done very well so as to ensure proper data communication. And, windows, android, Linux and Mac OS all support Zoom.

4) Live Private Chatting

Besides audio and video conferencing, Zoom has also incorporated live chatting panel. The chatting is not like the forum. Because, anyone can message anyone and its perfectly safe. The sessions are cleared on login logout too.

5) Animated Backgrounds

Animated Backgrounds is one of its prominent feature. In this feature suppose we have a messy background behind us, then we can remove or adjust the background by simply enabling the animated background features. The features include beach background, space background and many others. But, the feature works perfectly only on PCs with GPUs. On the basis of this feature, we can even say that zoom

uses AI integrated technology to detect faces and body and remove noises accordingly.

E. Google Meet

Google based products tend to have a huge amount of feature. Because more than 100s or more products are present in the market and one is responsive towards the other. Similarly, Google Meet as the name suggests is the Google application developed basically to conduct meetings and video conferencing. The Google Meet being part of the Google Ecosystem can be considered as an extended version of the Zoom because, there are features that the Zoom does not have. The most important feature among which is the dial up connection meeting. Sometimes due to electricity and many problems with internet it may not be possible for someone to connect to the meeting through the internet. So, Google Meet has an extended feature which allows a person to get connected through mobile network without internet connection. But, the main disadvantage is that it is only available for the premium users. The Google Meet architecture can be visualized in Fig. 10.

The various features of the Google Meet are:

1) Join By Phone

Join by Phone can be considered as the most prominent feature. Google Meet has an extended feature which allows a person to get connected through mobile network without internet connection. But, the main disadvantage is that it is only available for the premium users. Anyone offline or anyone without internet connection can join the meeting with their phones. Now, people from various remote areas with lack of internet can use this feature to join the meetings.

2) File Sharing

The another most useful feature of Google Meet is the file sharing. Unlike Zoom, the file sharing is possible. On Zoom, only messages were able to be sent to the particular users while Google Meet allows sharing of files too.

3) Web Based Application

Unlike various other video conferencing applications like zoom, teams, it is not necessary to download the application and run it. Because, the Google Meet is able to run just like messenger applications without being downloaded on to the host computer.

4) Backup

Sometimes it is necessary to backup data like recording live sessions. The recordings are automatically saved on to the Google Drive. The link can be then shared by the host. However, anyone cannot record live sessions, only host has the permission to record it. If other want to record the live sessions the host has to give the permission. Likewise, various file shared can be backed up immediately on to the google drive.

5) Cross Platform

The Google Meet is a cross platform application. The application can be used in any devices with the invite links opened. It is necessary to have Google account to join on to the Google Meet. Else, anonymous tags are applied automatically. They can run on Android, IOS, Linux, Windows and MacOS.

F. Cisco WebEx

Cisco WebEx is Web and Video conferencing application that is mostly used on the enterprise level by the large companies. Cisco offers Event Center, Support Center, Web Office, WebEx Meetings, WebEx Teams, etc. By the use of this tools and applications like Video Conferencing and Online meetings are handled using Cisco WebEx. Talking about the appearance, the Cisco WebEx has a chatting panel at the right side of the screen. The people on the meeting can be seen at the bottom. However, the design and appearances is poor. Files sharing is not possible in Cisco WebEx just like the Zoom meetings. The Cisco WebEx architecture can be visualized in Fig. 11.

Various features offered by Cisco WebEx are:

1) Security

Security is its major concern. All the video data and chats are encrypted. The host can easily remove the participants if the participants shift away from the rules. Only authorized users are able to join personalized meetings.

2) Web Based Application

It is a web based application so that there is no necessity to download any desktop or mobile applications. However, it consumes a little extra bandwidth compared to that of zoom or google meet. The sizes on the screen are customizable with change in the browser settings.

3) Cross Platform

The Cisco WebEx is a cross platform application. The application can be used in any devices with the invite links opened. It is necessary to have a temporary account to join on to the Cisco WebEx. They can run on Android, IOS, Linux, Windows and MacOS. However, the appearance may be different when different browsers are used.

4) Video Callback Desktop Clients

In the Cisco WebEx, the Desktop clients are able to call the non-desktop users to. There is a ID called the SIP. On the basis of the id, the desktop clients are able to call the non-desktop users.

5) Desktop Sharing

The Cisco WebEx also offers desktop sharing application because not only the hosts, the participants are also able to share desktop screens and do presentations. This can be a important feature on web based application.

Fig. 9. ZOOM

Fig. 10. Google Meet

Fig. 11. Cisco WebEx

V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ONLINE TEACHING LEARNING SYSTEMS

OTL systems tend to have plenty of features. The most important features of OTL Systems are Flexibility, convenience and consistency. However, the online teaching learning systems are a lot more challenging than they actually appear. Online teaching learning system may seem like more effortless to both the students and teachers because time delay rarely occur, class management need not be done, notes taking is rare and much more. There may be many disadvantages of getting an Online Teaching Learning systems, but there are a lot of advantages too. Taking both the positive and negative features I.e. the advantages and the disadvantages, various features of the online teaching learning systems are discussed and described below:

A. Usability

Usability refers to the user experience. Simply, usability refers to the easiness in the access or in the use of the product or platform. The platform should be able to understand what user want. A design is usable only if the user can find what he/she like is kept on the platform or not and his experience remains good with the platform. Basically, there are a way lot more personalized learning platforms as well as the online teaching learning platforms but not all have follow the usability property. That is why only few of them are able to persist on the market. According to ISO 9241-11 definition, usability is defined as “the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use.”[1]

The three outcomes of a usable platforms are:

- 1) *Effectiveness*
- 2) *Efficiency*
- 3) *Satisfaction*

B. Scalability

The needs and resources may increase with time. Scalability is the property of an organization to cope up with the increasing needs and still being able to perform well. Time is changing, scalability is the agility property. For an example, sometimes number of users on a platform may increase suddenly. In such cases, the server requests also becomes very high. When back up servers are not kept, the server may go down immediately. So, in order to cope up with situations like this, a backup server should be kept ready in uneven situations like these. Here, even if the workload increases, the platform is completely able to meet user needs. To expand globally, it's very necessary to understand the scalability property.

C. Security

Privacy is probably the greatest wealth. For a platform to have a long and stable run, the platform should be able to ensure the security of its users. During signing up, we enter various details on the platform. The details may even include our banking details and social security number. If the platform is not able ensure the security of our privacy then the platforms will be discarded and even reported for cases. Several hackers are always trying to steal our information every day, the OTL platforms should have strong firewall which the hackers can't barge into.

Several activities that ensure security in a platform are:

1) *The various server ports may have been opened for tunneling and maintenance which should be regularly checked and changed frequently.*

2) *The login and authentication can be done using secure google authentications.*

3) *The platform should have SSL certificates.*

4) *Backup servers should be kept up and running.*

5) *Honeypot networks should be made.*

6) *The IP id must not be made public and should be changed frequently in a very short time span.*

D. Supporting Multimedia

Learning is centered not only to reading books and articles. In fact, study shows that learning through video contents help us to understand better in a short span of time than directly reading the notes or books. Therefore, the platforms are more centered towards audio and video lectures rather than books and slide these days. The various multimedia are: Audio, Video, Pictures, text/documents, etc. The OTL platform allows us to share access all these on their platforms. However, MOOC systems do not allow sharing of multimedia from both the ends. MOOC allows sharing through a single end only and the single end is of the tutor or the Mentor. While online video conferencing applications allow sharing of videos, audios and even screens. But, many of the online video conferencing applications like ZOOM, Cisco WebEx do not allow sharing of the files while there are also conferencing applications like Google Meet and Google classrooms that allow sharing of text files/documents too.

E. Heterogeneity

On the basis of time zones and availability, our preferences are different. Heterogenous is the principal of being different from one another on the same group. Consider an example, if we are to access a cross platform application, then we can use the application from any devices like: Mobile, Tablets, Laptops, etc. We can even us the device from different operating systems like: Android, IOS, Linux, Windows, etc. In fact we can even use the application from different browsers too like: Chrome, Firefox, Edge, etc. The principal of heterogeneity depends on our preferences. Here, our IP, MAC addresses are all different. Our screen sizes are different, the fonts and layouts we have been using are different. The platforms should therefore be heterogenous. Everything defined should be made universal so that any device can run with the universal defined content. The content should be made available for all. The OTL platforms should be able to cope up with heterogeneity.

F. Reliability

Reliability of a platforms are not defined only by a single factor. There are several contributing factors like Performance, Security, Memory, etc. that defines the reliability of the platform. An OTL system is said to be reliable if it can perform well under user given conditions. The response time of the system should be fast. The latency should be minimized as far as possible. Moreover, the platform should not be made complex. And, there are several measures to check reliability. One measure way is to check though feedback forms and surveys. The other popular measure ways are defined by the platform themselves. For e.g. the videos and audios on MOOC platforms can be verified with the original writers and research scientists. While the ZOOM, Teams are

check via slow internet connections. In this way, the reliability is checked for a platform.

G. Availability

Various platforms are developed and deployed in the specific regions only. Every courses may not be available in every specific regions. Almost every courses are available for developed countries like Europe, America and its sub continents. Popular example being Udacity paid version not available in Asia. While sometimes courses are available only for developing countries or only South Asian Countries only.

But, most of all being available is not only about the regions the platform is active on. The availability is also defined on the basis of the time the platform remains active on the internet. So, availability of a platform can be defined as the amount of time the platform remains active out of the total time. Sometimes system maintenance may lead to server being down for a longer span of time. In order to deal with this problem and increase the availability time, backup servers should be kept up and running.

H. Privacy

Privacy is the concern of security. Privacy is probably our greatest wealth. Our private information involves out Names, Email Ids, phone numbers, web address, local address, public Ip, etc. These information are really valuable because on the basis of these information hackers can easily barge into our computers and personal life through social engineering. So, privacy need to be ensured by the OTL systems of its users. Sometimes, we may have to even upload our banking account numbers or even the social security numbers. If these things are publicly available to everyone then we may be really doomed. Therefore, privacy is the major concern on the OTL systems and we should not enter our private details without any knowledge on these platforms.

I. Affordability/Cost

Affordability or the costs are the major concern on all OTL systems. Because almost every OTL systems are paid besides few open source platforms. Generally, what it's like on an OTL system is that, the advanced and intermediate courses are expensive while the beginner courses are free. The beginner courses are too simple and most of the time is very less useful. The courses on the OTL systems like Udacity are even ranging up to \$1200 and more. These courses are pretty expensive and the platforms are hugely profit motive. But, few platforms like Coursera are also there which offer financial aids for the needy ones. The financial aid allows even premium courses for free which is also their great initiation for online learning revolution. So, affordability or the cost might probably be one of the prominent feature to earn maximum users and gaining popularity.

J. QoS

QoS or the quality of service is able to define how the services provided by the platform are. The quality can be either good or bad. The measure of the quality of service can be done by the feedbacks provided by the users. Also, the number of users engagement or the number of subscribers of the platform can decide the QoS. Generally, the forums also can be a medium to decide the QoS because people tend to

express their feeling as a comments on the forums. Surveys can also be another options.

K. Performance

Performance itself is a broad term. But, on the basis of general understanding, the performance can be reckoned as measure that defines how fast or slow a particular OTL system is. Because, sometimes, to make the platforms attractive the developers and designers tend to use a lot of designs and animations which in turn makes the platform heavy and longer time to load. The response time increases because of too much JavaScript. For better performance the server should also be stable. Old and small servers easily break down on too many requests. So, these things should be taken care of to maintain seamless performance.

L. Maintainability

Maintenance is the probably the main part in a software engineering project. Almost every time the application may suffer breakdowns when new changes are made on it. The maintainability is the property that allows the application to run safe and sound by moving along with problems and their solutions. It can be referred to the degree wo which an application is understood, enhanced or repaired by the users and developers.

M. Modifiability

This is the another property that comes around Maintainability. The application has to come up with the changing demands of people with time. Time and again new updates are launched. This brings new changes in the platform. Features are added by following the property of modifiability. New versions are launched because of it. This property really help particular application to remain stable on market by adjusting with the increasing human needs. The platforms need to be modifiable so that new improvements can be made on it.

N. Accessibility

This is also an important topic to talk about. Generally the OTL systems are cross platform. That meaning they can be accessed by most of the electronic devices that is connected to the internet. Also, there is no particular preference on which browsers or operating systems to use to access the OTL systems. Because of this important feature the online teaching and learning has become much more efficient and effective. It has become easy to access as well. Moreover, accessibility can also be a disadvantage to the security because anyone with the link can join the OTL systems on most of the applications unless the host has changed the settings. So, accessibility is one of the important feature of online teaching learning systems.

Table. 1. Comparison between OTL systems

	Moodle	Google Classroom	ZOOM	Google Meet	MOOC	Cisco Webex
Usability	Poor in older versions and mobile phones	Easy to use	Easy to use	Easy to use	Platform Dependent	Minor Issue for Beineers
Scalability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Security	Host Dependent	Secure	Poor	Secure	Host Dependent	Secure
Supporting Multimedia	Audio, Video, Files	Audio, Video, Files	Audio, Video	Audio, Video, Files	Audio, Video, Files	Audio, Video
Heterogeneity	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Reliability	Reliable, Offline Access	Reliable	Unreliable with Video Call timing	Reliable	Reliable based on Organisation	Reliable
Availability	Available	Available	Available	Available	Available	Available
Privacy	Dependent on Organisation	Encrypted	Privacy Issue	Encrypted	Encrypted	Dependent on Organisation
Affordability/ Cost	Open Source	Free / Premium	Free / Premium	Free / Premium	Mostly Paid, Organisation Dependent	Free / Premium
QoS	6	1	3	2	4	5
Performance	Not Perfect all the time, various plugin need improvements	Good	Good	Good	Good but more dependent on organisation	Good
Maintainability	Regular	Regular	Regular	Regular	Regular	Regular
Modifiability	Modifiable	Modifiable	Modifiable	Modifiable	Modifiable	Modifiable
Accessibility	Accessible	Accessible	Accessible	Accessible	Accessible	Accessible
Testability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concurrency	Yes	Yes	Doesnot save messages on login logout	Yes	Yes	Doesnot save messages on login logout
Convenience	Can be improved	Convenient	Convenient	Convenient	Convenient	Convenient

O. Testability

Testability is another important property on OTL systems. Without testing of the product, the product that appears on the market is insecure and may have several faults whose break downs can be well anticipated. There is a separate team set of for software testing who test the software using various testing tools. The popular examples of testing are: Unit testing, gdb, etc. Various real world test cases are self-generated and on the basis of those test cases, particular applications are tested. Without testing, an application may run well but with time the problems with scalability, security, etc. can occur. And, such applications may even break down on unanticipated user inputs. So, testability is one of the important property of OTL systems.

P. Concurrency

Generally in an OTL systems, the contents are managed on a cloud server. By contents, the meaning can be file sharing, the audio, video lectures, etc. Due to this feature the platform can be accessed from anywhere at any time. The concurrency is a prominent feature because one does not have to lose a live sessions because of concurrency. We can go and check out the audios, videos and notes and assignments at any time we like. There is a database storage. When the user requests for contents, request is made on to the database and we get to see the contents. If we make any changes, the same contents are saved on to the database. If we try to login from a different place or different device we still get the same content because they are stored on Universal database. This feature is known as concurrency.

Q. Convenience

The OTL systems are convenient to use. They are made convenient so as to have a large community of subscribers or the users. The graphical user interface features make it convenient to use. They are built with aim to fulfill the demands of children to young adults to old people with enthusiasm to learn something new. Also, various help bars and notifications guide us through on how to use the platform. Some OTL systems like MOOC even have chat bot systems enabled which even replied the queries. The chatbot systems are really helpful. So, concluding all the convenience is the property that tends us to use the platform. So, the OTL systems should be made convenient to use.

VI. DISCUSSION/WAY FORWARD

OTL systems are already much more advanced systems with tremendous amount of features. But with time, several features might need to be added to the OTL systems so as to cope up with changing requirements. The feature requirements are determined on the basis of feedbacks from the both course instructors and the learners. Following are the various fields that an OTL system can have an improvement on:

A. IT Law

The online teaching learning system is the exponentially growing field. By 2025, it is even estimated to grow into a market size of \$351 billion. But, however the more growth and reach it has, the more losses will it face when it is breached or hacked down. Since, getting hacked on millions of dollars as

well as millions of user information is not a new news. These actions give a tremendous loss to both the companies getting hacked down and the public losing money and information. There are several types of hacking and breaching activities that has been widely popular since past. Some hacking techniques are: SQL injections, DDOS attacks, Cross-Site Scripting, Inclusion attacks, Access Control attacks, etc. A proper law is not made and in existent at the current moment. Who is to bear the loss of all the user personal details. There are no defined laws, rules and regulations. So, a proper IT or the Cyber law should be amended so as to ensure the security and privacy of the users. With the widely growing market of online teaching learning system, the OTL field is at a risk so proper cyber/IT laws should be amended and necessary measures should be taken instantaneously.

B. Socioeconomic Status

Socio-Economic Status effects a lot on Online Teaching Learning (OTL) systems. According to a research, it is said that the poor students are said to achieve poor grades too. According to the research conducted among a mass of 8000 students on over 42 schools, it was found to be deducted. It is not just in a particular country but through the World. The researchers at Harvard and MIT University were completely shocked by the result, so they conducted other research and came into conclusion that there is a link between family income, academic achievement and brain anatomy. But, besides all this researches and studies, there are many examples of student who have stand out of every one. Many have created space for themselves in the book of history too. Most of all it is the duty of the course instructor and mentor to take care of these things. Because, it's the duty of the course instructor to ensure if everyone is getting just the right things they need or not. As well as, the education along with the other resources should be equally imparted to everyone. Education should not be oriented towards money only.

C. Depth of technology

The OTL system makes use of many technologies. The technology used by the OTL systems were not primarily developed for OTL systems. They were developed for separate purpose. However, by the use of these technologies, the online teaching and learning has progressed in an extensive way. For an example, gamification in quizzes. Due to gamification, the quizzes appear very interactive and enjoyable to solve. Other examples can be chatting systems, video and audio calls, etc. The purpose of chatting system was to communicate but the use of chatting on OTL systems give a separate approach to collaborating with the other fellow learners. Also, the video call and audio call technologies has made it easier to attend live teaching sessions. But, however while talking about the depth of the technology countrywide, several number of features are there that are limited to the developing countries. The developing and the underdeveloped countries do not tend to have a good internet connection. Because of this the videos keep on buffering and do not tend to render. It could be solved by using the separate networks and increasing the number of towers so as to improve the communication. Internet should be cheaper and then only the technology can have a real impact on the education and its prosper.

D. Infrastructure Supported

The OTL system might appear a very easy implementation but in fact it is way more difficult. There are several infrastructures that plays the vital role for successful online

teaching and learning. The most vital components without which the OTL systems might even no exist are:

- 1) *Hardware*
- 2) *Software*
- 3) *Support Team*

When it comes to OTL systems then the hardware requirements like Laptops or Desktop or mobile phones are the things of concern. Everyone is not self-sufficient with technological goods like these. And when it comes to teaching online, the teachers might probably require touch pens to draw on the screen. Everyone does not have it. Hardware requirements is that's why another challenge for the online teaching and learning system. Moreover, software can be a challenge too. Because, there are lots of software that are not open source. And, when we are necessarily to use such software on our day to day life for doing projects and much more we require license key. We have to buy them. Buying them is another challenge in the economy too. Sometimes we may have both hardware and software system, but one may not support another because of the version problems. Sometimes, the hardware or software may be outdated compared to each other too. And moreover, support team is also another primary infrastructure supported. Because, while using various OTL systems, we may encounter several errors. The error may be either solved by ourselves or even could persist on the system making the whole server down. In this cases, the support team play a major role to inspect the server, find the errors and also rectify the errors too. Each of the above mentioned factors are to be developed and well implemented for a successful OTL systems.

VII. CONCLUSION

A complete research was done in the field of OTL Systems. The knowledge gained from the internet research and questionnaires among related users gave an insight about the inline details of an OTL system. The primary components of an OTL systems are the tutor and the students where the tutor teaches a single or a group of students over the internet through various platforms. The basic architectures along with the platforms are also discussed of an Online Teaching Learning system. Almost about 2 weeks of research, case studies and google searches made it finally possible to complete the research paper.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

Although, the OTL systems are way more advanced at the current scenario. But, there are still rooms for improvements. Following are some several areas on which the OTL systems can be improved. The following mentioned points also depicts that following are the limitations of the OTL systems at current situation. Future enhancements can be done by:

- a) *Implementation of proper IT Laws*
- b) *Integration of Financial Aid for economically challenged person*
- c) *Open Sourcing the Contents*
- d) *Integration of Firewall to ensure security*
- e) *Platform based data encryption system*
- f) *Enabling private mentor ship for students*
- g) *Increasing the tutor to student ratio, etc.*

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